

Multi-Fidelity Learning with Shallow Recurrent Decoders for Reactor Physics

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ABSTRACT

In reactor physics, neutronics can be treated with different fidelity levels, according to the needs of the user. On one hand, the precise modeling of neutrons' behaviour in reactor physics is often expensive and time-consuming due to the high computational costs to numerically solve the Boltzmann transport equation. Conversely, by adopting suitable assumptions, such as the SP_N , diffusion theory, and point kinetics, it is possible to generate efficiently low-fidelity data. From the perspective of surrogate models, this computational limitation translates into a scarcity of high-fidelity data and a significant amount of low-fidelity data. Given this difference in fidelity levels, it would be interesting to develop a suitable procedure to map low-fidelity models towards higher fidelity models; for instance, one could obtain the solution to a multi-group diffusion equation starting from time-series data obtained from a point kinetics model. Indeed, this work investigates this possibility by leveraging multi-fidelity information with Shallow Recurrent Decoders, a novel machine learning architecture able to map time-series observations to the full state of the reactor. This technique has been designed to use local or global measurements as input and map their temporal trajectories to the high-dimensional state; by the same logic, in principle, this architecture can also be used when the input is formed by the solution of a lumped model. This work applies this idea to a benchmark reactor geometry, mapping the point kinetics model to the diffusion solution under various input conditions, with much less computational costs.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Multi-fidelity, Neutronics, Shallow Recurrent Decoders

1. INTRODUCTION

The accurate prediction of neutronics behaviour in nuclear reactors is fundamental for safety analysis, design optimization, and monitoring applications. However, the numerical solution of high-fidelity mathematical models, represented by systems of coupled partial differential equations such as the one arising from the discretisation of the Boltzmann transport equation [1], is computationally demanding even on high-performance computers. This drawback limits their use for multi-query scenarios, as in optimisation tasks or uncertainty quantification [2], in which multiple evaluations of the model are needed. In order to tackle this shortcoming, Reduced-Order Modelling (ROM) techniques have been extensively used in the nuclear engineering community to provide fast yet reliable approximations of high-fidelity solutions [3]. These algorithms are divided into two main categories: projection-based methods, in which the governing equations are projected onto a low-dimensional subspace; and non-intrusive/data-driven methods, in which the reduced model is learnt from data. The latter, even though they might predict unphysical solutions if not properly trained, come with greater flexibility compared to projection-based methods, since the same framework can be applied to different problems with few

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modifications on the code implementation. Alongside ROM methodologies, low-fidelity models, relying on simplifying assumptions to reduce the computational burden, have been widely adopted in reactor physics: for instance, lumped models based on the Point Kinetics (PK) equations have been extensively used for plant simulations and control, especially given the large computational burden of high-fidelity neutronics models. The PK equations can be considered as an projection-based ROM of the neutron transport equation following Henry's approach, by projecting the equations using the adjoint. Only with the recent increase in computational power have more accurate models, such as multi-group diffusion and transport models, become computationally feasible. As such, there is a relative abundance of low-fidelity data and a rather scarcity of high-fidelity models, which makes neutronics analysis an interesting field for studying multi-fidelity (MF) learning approaches. The key idea of MF is to exploit information from multiple sources of different accuracy and computational cost. The recent advances in Machine Learning (ML) and reduced-order modeling offer new perspectives for combining low- and high-fidelity descriptions of reactor physics phenomena [4, 5].

Among ML and ROM techniques, Shallow Recurrent Decoders (SHRED) have emerged as a powerful paradigm [6, 7, 8] capable of estimating a high-dimensional field from sparse time-series measurements with great accuracy. Compared to other state estimation methods, SHRED presents several promising advantages: (i) it can work with very few measurements; (ii) it is agnostic to sensor positions; (iii) it requires minimal hyperparameter tuning. In its original formulation, SHRED uses sparse sensor measurements to reconstruct the full state of the system, making this framework an optimal solution for the monitoring tasks within the development of digital twins [9]. However, design and optimisation tasks are performed before building the actual facility, hence measurements are not available, making the state estimation process for control and monitoring not directly possible. Given this apparent limitation, Faraji et al. [10] have shown that it is possible to train a SHRED model also using global measurements for the prediction of plasma dynamics; therefore, it is legitimate to investigate the possibility of generating a reduced-order model of some high-fidelity model, such as diffusion or transport, starting from temporal trajectories coming from a low-fidelity model, like the PK one. In this way, it would be possible to obtain accurate estimations of high-fidelity models with the computational cost of low-fidelity ones, thus deriving a reduced-order model suitable for reactor physics applications before deployment. This work investigates this possibility, considering a benchmark test case based on the LRA benchmark geometry from Argonne Benchmark Book [11], with the goal of mapping a PK model to a two-group diffusion solution.

2. SHALLOW RECURRENT DECODERS FOR MULTI-FIDELITY LEARNING

The novel framework represented by Shallow Recurrent Decoders has been shown to be a powerful technique that can map sparse measurements to the corresponding high-dimensional state; it has been successfully applied to different physics, ranging from climate modelling, fluid dynamics, nuclear reactor modelling, and biology [6, 7, 8]. The SHRED architecture is composed of a recurrent unit, typically a Long Short-Term Memory network (LSTM), and a shallow decoder (SDN); the former learns a suitable latent space from temporal trajectories, whereas the latter maps this learnt space to the high-dimensional one. Both components of SHRED have two layers each (with 64 neurons each for the recurrent unit and 350 and 400 neurons for the latter), making the overall network relatively small; furthermore, this architecture requires minimal hyperparameter tuning, since the same number of neurons and layers can be used for different applications. Previous studies have also shown that the network can work in compressive mode, in which the output of the shallow decoder lies in the reduced space obtained by Singular Value Decomposition (SVD): the high-dimensional state can then be retrieved by projecting the learnt latent dynamics onto the spatial modes computed with the SVD. This solution reduces both the training database and the output size, and consequently the training time, allowing for training even on personal computers. Most of the applications of SHRED have been for monitoring purposes in the broad framework of state estimation problems, focusing on the reconstruction from sparse measurements. This task has been successfully applied for reconstruction, predictions, and forecasting

Figure 1. Scheme of the Multi-Fidelity SHRED (MF-SHRED), where the solution of the point kinetics equations is mapped to the high-fidelity diffusion model.

scenarios, and for multi-physics problems considering only a single observable field [8, 9]; in particular, it has been shown that very few input sensors (around 3 to 5) are enough to obtain an accurate state estimation, due to the fact that temporal histories are given as input to the recurrent unit: this ensures a deeper knowledge as stated by the Takens time-delay embedding theorem. The SHRED architecture has been implemented in Python using the Pytorch package; the original code [6] has been adapted for the present application, and it is openly available at github.com/ERMETE-Lab/NuSHRED, as well as the notebooks used to generate the results.

This work expands the use of SHRED for multi-fidelity reduced order modelling, following the development from Conti et al. in [4, 5] on this topic. Even though local measurements have been generally used as input for the SHRED architecture, it is also possible to adopt global measurements [10], such as the power level of a nuclear reactor or a lumped temperature value. This is possible because the recurrent unit only requires time-series data, and it does not need information on how the data was collected. Accordingly, this allows for the use of lower-fidelity models as input for the SHRED architecture, to map them to a high-fidelity model and thus enabling the use of SHRED for multi-query applications as a ROM of the reactor, in which the spatial behaviour is encoded in the SVD modes and the dynamics are given by the neural network itself. This idea is depicted in Figure 1, where the solution of the Point Kinetics equations is mapped to the high-fidelity diffusion model; once the network has been trained, the solution for a new reactivity profile can be computed by simply solving the point kinetics and then feeding it to the trained SHRED, thus obtaining an estimation of the diffusion solution. In principle, this procedure can also be extended to multi-step fidelity learning: for example, from diffusion to transport or from coarse to fine mesh.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS ON THE LRA BENCHMARK PROBLEM

The MF-SHRED methodology has been tested on a test case, based on the geometry of the LRA BWR benchmark problem from the Argonne Benchmark Book [11]. The geometry is shown in Figure 2, along with the numerical mesh used to discretise the diffusion equation: it includes six different regions, five of which are multiplying media (except for the external region with ID = 50). Even though similar results can be obtained using the group cross sections from the original benchmark problem, it has been chosen to generate the group cross sections using OpenMC to show the flexibility of the approach as a

Figure 2. Geometry, numerical mesh and regions of the LRA benchmark.

multi-fidelity learning process, which could be applied to different neutronic problems.

Two models have been implemented for this case: a low-fidelity one based on the PK equations with two groups of precursors (for the sake of simplicity and to show that only 3 input "measurements" are needed by the SHRED architecture, in the future this limitation can be overcome and adopt an ensemble approach for SHRED [8]) and a high-fidelity two-energy group diffusion model. The PK model, which has been solved in Python, using the *solve_ivp* solver from the *scipy* library, reads as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dP}{dt} = \frac{\rho(t; \boldsymbol{\mu}) - \beta}{\Lambda} P + \sum_{j=1}^J \lambda_j c_j & (1a) \\ \frac{dc_j}{dt} = \frac{\beta_j}{\Lambda} P - \lambda_j c_j & (1b) \end{cases}$$

where P is the reactor power, c_j is the concentration of the j -th precursors group, $\rho(t; \boldsymbol{\mu})$ is the reactivity, β is the total delayed neutron fraction, β_j is the delayed neutron fraction of the j -th group, Λ is the neutron generation time, and λ_j is the decay constant of the j -th precursors group; in the end, $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ represents a vector of parameters specific to the undergoing transient starting from criticality conditions. The multi-group diffusion equation, with ϕ_g as the neutron flux of the g -th group and c_j the j -th precursors groups, reads:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{1}{v_g} \frac{\partial \phi_g}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (D_g \nabla \phi_g) - \left(\Sigma_{a,g}(t; \boldsymbol{\mu}) + \sum_{g' \neq g} \Sigma_{s,g \rightarrow g'} \right) \phi_g + \sum_{g' \neq g} \Sigma_{s,g' \rightarrow g} \phi_{g'} + \chi_g S_g & (2a) \\ \frac{\partial c_j}{\partial t} = \frac{\beta_j}{k_{\text{eff}}} \sum_g v_g \Sigma_{f,g} \phi_g - \lambda_j c_j & (2b) \end{cases}$$

with $S_g = \frac{1-\beta}{k_{\text{eff}}} \sum_{g'} v_{g'} \Sigma_{f,g'} \phi_{g'} + \sum_j \lambda_j c_j$ being the neutron source term. The system starts from initial critical conditions and the boundary conditions are zero flux on the external boundary of the domain (top and right sides) and reflective on the internal boundaries (left and bottom sides). This system of partial differential equations has been discretised using the finite element method, provided by the open-source package *dolfinx* (version 0.7.0) and adopting the code developed by the authors in [12] (which can be found at github.com/ERMETE-Lab/MP-OFELIA). Transient behaviour is triggered by modifying the absorption cross section $\Sigma_{a,2}(\mathbf{x}, t; \boldsymbol{\mu})$ of the thermal group in the rod region (ID = 60), $\mathbf{x} \in \Omega_{\text{rod}}$, from the nominal value $\Sigma_{a,2}^{(0)}(\mathbf{x})$ as follows: $\Sigma_{a,2}(\mathbf{x}, t; \boldsymbol{\mu}) = \Sigma_{a,2}^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}) \cdot f(t; \boldsymbol{\mu})$. The function f depends

on time and on parameters identifying the specific transient under which the system undergoes (such as the height of a step or the end time of a ramp). A similar input condition is given to the PK model through reactivity $\rho(t, \boldsymbol{\mu})$.

Three different profiles for the absorption cross section have been studied, namely ramp, sinusoidal, and trapezoidal signals. The general form of these functions is given below, dependent on different parameters $\mu_1 \in [0.97, 1.03]$, $\mu_2 \in [0.2, 0.8]$, $\mu_3 \in [0.2, 0.75]$ and $\mu_4 \in [0.2, 0.79]$: the first one represents the final value of the modified cross section $\pm 3\%$, the second and fourth ones are the end time of the rising ramp, whereas the third one is the period of the oscillation.

$$f_{\text{ramp}}(t; \boldsymbol{\mu}) = \begin{cases} 1 + (\mu_1 - 1) \cdot \frac{t}{\mu_2} & 0 \leq t \leq \mu_2 \\ \mu_1 & t > \mu_2 \end{cases} \quad (3a)$$

$$f_{\text{sin}}(t; \boldsymbol{\mu}) = 1 + \frac{\mu_1 - 1}{2} \cdot \left(1 - \cos\left(\frac{2\pi t}{\mu_3}\right) \right) \quad (3b)$$

$$f_{\text{trapez}}(t; \boldsymbol{\mu}) = \begin{cases} 1 + (\mu_1 - 1) \cdot \frac{t}{\mu_4} & 0 \leq t \leq \mu_4 \\ \mu_1 & \mu_2 < t \leq 0.8 \cdot T_{\text{final}} \\ 1 + (\mu_1 - 1) \cdot \frac{T_{\text{final}} - t}{T_{\text{final}} \cdot (1 - 0.8)} & t > 0.8 \cdot T_{\text{final}} \end{cases} \quad (3c)$$

The equivalent functions for the reactivity profiles are not reported for the sake of brevity (see the NuSHRED Github repository, if interested). The dataset is composed of 50 parametric solutions for the ramp, 50 for the sinusoidal, and 50 for the trapezoidal shape, with a transient up to $T_{\text{final}} = 4$ s. The snapshots from the diffusion and the PK have been split into train ($\sim 70\%$), test ($\sim 20\%$), and validation ($\sim 10\%$) sets, adopting random splitting on the parametric space. The diffusion high-dimensional state includes the neutron fluxes (2 groups) and the precursor concentrations (2 groups).

Figure 3. Average wall-clock time, in seconds, needed to obtain a solution from each modelling methods: the diffusion requires much more time, whereas the PK and the MF-SHRED (including decoding with SVD) have comparable time.

The first step of the MF-SHRED procedure consists of reducing the high-dimensional state with the Singular Value Decomposition, retaining only 3 modes for each field (such that more than 99.99% of the information is contained as per decay of the singular values, not reported here for sake of brevity); the reduced coefficients, encoding the temporal dynamics, are obtained by projecting the high-fidelity snapshots to the low-rank space, and the SHRED architecture learns them from the low-fidelity solution in a supervised framework. The solutions of the PK equations, represented by power and precursor concentrations, are the input for the network. Training takes around 1 minute on a MacBook Pro M4 with the GPU via the Metal Performance Shaders (MPS) backend, and 5 minutes using the CPU instead; following training, the MF-SHRED is tested on unknown parametric scenarios (either from ramp, sine,

Figure 4. Temporal evolution of the normalised spatial average $\langle \psi(\mathbf{x})(t, \boldsymbol{\mu}^*) \rangle / \langle \psi(\mathbf{x}; 0, \boldsymbol{\mu}^*) \rangle$ of the different fields, normalised with respect to the initial condition (continuous line is the diffusion, dashed line is the MF-SHRED prediction).

Figure 5. Contour plots (the fluxes are normalised to have total reactor power equal to 1) at the last time step for a test parameter (sinusoidal transient with $\mu_1 \approx 1.08$ and $\mu_3 \approx 0.8095$) of the fast flux ϕ_1 (first column), thermal flux ϕ_2 (second column), first precursors group c_1 (third column) and second precursors group c_2 (fourth). From left to right: high-fidelity solution, estimation with MF-SHRED, the associated the residual field. The prediction with SHRED provides a correct local state estimation.

and trapezoid), and the relative test error is computed as follows for the generic field ψ :

$$\varepsilon_2^\psi = \frac{1}{N_s^{test}} \sum_{n=1}^{N_s^{test}} \left(\frac{1}{N_t} \sum_{j=1}^{N_t} \frac{\|\Psi_j^{\mu_n} - \hat{\Psi}_j^{\mu_n}\|_2}{\|\Psi_j^{\mu_n}\|_2} \right) \quad (4)$$

The relative test error for each field with respect the diffusion solution is generally low, specifically

$$\varepsilon_2^{\phi_1} = 0.0187 \pm 0.0111; \quad \varepsilon_2^{\phi_2} = 0.0134 \pm 0.0079; \quad \varepsilon_2^{c_1} = 0.00032 \pm 0.00023; \quad \varepsilon_2^{c_2} = 0.00071 \pm 0.00051 \quad (5)$$

It can be observed that the difference between the estimated quantities and the high-fidelity diffusion solution is very low, meaning that all the fields are, on average, accurately reconstructed. In addition to the accuracy of MF-SHRED, it is important to assess the efficiency of the approach, namely, its associated computational time. All the operations have been performed on the same machine, and it has been chosen to use the wall-clock time as a metric for the computational performance: even though the training of SHRED is typically done on laptop GPUs, being more efficient, it has been decided to use a CPU to have a fairer comparison with the finite element solution and the PK integration. Figure 3 shows the wall clock time, expressed in seconds, that each model requires to obtain a full solution of the transient for a new parameter value. The diffusion solved with finite elements needs around 3 seconds, whereas the PK and the MF-SHRED (including the decoding with SVD, being a matrix-vector multiplication) take less than 0.01 seconds, for a gain in the computational times of more than 2 orders of magnitude.

After assessing that globally the estimation with MF-SHRED is accurate by measuring the error, it is possible to observe how the reconstruction behaves both in time and space: Figure 4 shows the spatial average of each estimated field over time for different parameters in the test set (from each transient type), normalised with respect to the initial condition; Figure 5 shows instead the contour plot of the different fields, comparing the diffusion solution with the estimation with MF-SHRED, including the associated residual field (i.e., the absolute difference). It can be observed that the dynamics are always well predicted and that the architecture is able to discriminate the specific transient under consideration and reconstruct the state accurately; this is not only true for the global quantities, but also locally. The decoding layers and the SVD allow for representing the spatial behaviour in a compact way, making the overall architecture generally cheap to train and thus enabling quick estimations.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper investigates the use of Shallow Recurrent Decoders for multi-fidelity learning and, more broadly, for reduced-order modeling. Previous studies focused on the monitoring capabilities of this architecture, proving that it can map sparse sensor measurements to the high-dimensional state. This work has shown that it is possible to use SHRED to also map low-fidelity models, such as lumped models, to high-fidelity models based on partial differential equations: specifically, this paper has focused on reactor physics, mapping the point kinetics to the multi-group diffusion equation for a simple problem based on a neutronic benchmark. The results obtained from this analysis are really promising, showing that the MF-SHRED architecture is generally accurate in predicting the higher-fidelity solution for different transients with much cheaper computational costs. These results motivate further investigation of this methodology for reduced-order modelling applications of SHRED for reactor physics. Future developments involve the extension of this framework to more complex scenarios, considering more realistic reactors like the TRIGA Mark II, and introducing thermal feedbacks. In addition, this methodology can also be included in a multi-step procedure where the learning process can pass from point kinetics to diffusion to even higher-fidelity models like transport. In the end, this framework can be adopted to other fidelity levels, for instance, for coarse to fine mesh discretisation.

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